

Conference abstract

Relationship between academic engagement and burnout syndrome in Mexican students: a PLS-SEM analysis

Irving A. Ramírez-Muñoz¹, Vanesa Avalos-Gaytán^{1,*}, Igor Barahona², Valeria Soto-Mendoza¹, and Gabriela Linares Acuña³

¹Universidad Autónoma de Coahuila, Centro de Investigación en Matemáticas Aplicadas, Unidad Saltillo, Mexico.

²King Fahd University of Petroleum and Minerals, Department of Information Systems and Operations Management, Dhahran, Saudi Arabia.

³Universidad Autónoma de Coahuila, Facultad de Psicología, Unidad Saltillo, Mexico.

ABSTRACT

Academic burnout is a growing concern in higher education, characterized by emotional exhaustion, cynicism, and a reduced sense of accomplishment. In contrast, academic engagement – defined as a positive, energetic, and committed state toward learning – has been identified as a protective factor and even an antidote to burnout. While most studies in this area have focused either on theoretical model development or on validating measurement instruments, few address both simultaneously. Moreover, research using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) has predominantly been conducted in Europe and the United States, leaving Latin American contexts underexplored. A literature review revealed only nine studies on academic burnout in Mexico, underscoring the need for further investigation in the region. This study aims to bridge that gap by validating adapted versions of the Maslach Burnout Inventory-Student Survey (MBI-SS) and the School Engagement Measure, and by developing a SEM to examine how academic engagement influences burnout levels among students at a public university in northern Mexico. The findings are expected to contribute to the understanding of student well-being in Latin America and to offer validated tools for measuring and addressing academic burnout.

Keywords: burnout syndrome, academic engagement, structural equation model

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